

The Arrow Points Left: Visions of Social Transformation in the PFLP's First Decade

Introduction

In the 1980s West Bank and Gaza there rose multiple developmental initiatives undertaken by the Popular Front for the Liberation of Palestine (PFLP), such as farmers and women's cooperatives. These cooperatives point to a socioeconomically transformative agenda that the party practiced. Yet in the seminal book, *Armed Struggle and the Search for State*, Yezid Sayigh argues that factions of the Palestinian Liberation Organization (PLO), including the PFLP, lacked a socially transformative political program. Their nationalist emphasis and their reliance on regional support arguably led to rent-seeking neopatrimonial politics, even amongst leftist parties and their grassroots organizations in the Occupied Palestinian Territories (OPT), and despite the radical social and economic development rhetoric they employed.¹

This working paper is propelled by Sayigh's argument but takes a step back to examine in detail the visions, or rhetoric, of the PFLP for traces of socioeconomic transformation. It does this by studying the PFLP's mouthpiece, *Al-Hadaf* magazine, between the second congress of the PFLP in 1969 and up to 1979, with a focus on the spatial components of such visions.²

In this paper I argue that while the PFLP projected little visions of social transformation in its official strategy, its mouthpiece *Al-Hadaf* presents such visions in two indirect forms: 1) models of building socialism taken from other revolutions, and 2) visions for national democratic revolutions in Arab countries.

From this preliminary inspection, a number of intersections between *Al-Hadaf's* rhetoric and the developmental line of the PFLP's OPT organization appear—such as a focus on the agrarian question. At this point, however, it is not possible to conclusively determine the reasons or significance of such intersections.

¹ Yezid Sayigh, *Al-kifah al-musallah wa al-baht `an al-dawlat: al-harakat al-wataniyyat al-filastiniyyat 1949-1993*. Muassasat al-dirasat al-filastiniyya, 2011, p. 856-857.

² The research stops at the 10-year mark due to the limited availability of sources at the time of writing. A more meaningful endpoint would have been the fourth congress of the PFLP in 1981, while the aspiration is for this research to cover the period until the fifth congress in 1993. Furthermore, the first 54 issues of *Al-Hadaf* were not available for analysis this research.

Background

The Popular Front for the Liberation of Palestine (PFLP) was founded in 1967 with its aim as the liberation of the full land of Palestine, and its general strategy being guerilla warfare that develops into a traditional war of liberation.³ In its second congress, in 1969, the PFLP adopted Marxism-Leninism and declared its goal as the destruction of the state of Israel and the establishment of a democratic national state in Palestine where Arabs and Jews will live as citizens with equal rights.⁴ In this congress, the PFLP pronounced China, Vietnam, and Cuba as models for its strategy, broadly following a Maoist line.⁵

By the end of the 70s, the PFLP's congress and politburo publications would have voiced a call for a socialist Arab society, announced economic struggle as dialectically tied to political struggle, and called on the working class and its parties and allies to achieve the national and socialist revolutions as one operation in multiple phases, led by the working class.⁶ Nonetheless, the nature of such transformation remained vague in these documents, and mostly deferred to a second phase of struggle. However, *Al-Hadaf* provides clues as to the topics that might have concerned the PFLP in this social transformation as well as the party's sources of influence.

Visions in *Al-Hadaf*

Visions of social transformation appear in *Al-Hadaf* in two main forms:

³ Al-Jabha al-Sha'biyya li-Tahrir Filastin, "Al-Bayan al-Ta'sisi al-Awwal li-l-Jabha al-Sha'biyya li-Tahrir Filastin (The Founding Statement of the Popular Front for the Liberation of Palestine)" December 11, 1967.

⁴ Al-Jabha al-Sha'biyya li-Tahrir Filastin, *Al-Istratijiyya al-Siyasiyya wa al-Tanzimiyya (Political and Organisational Strategy)*, 1969, p. 42.

⁵ *Ibid*, p. 27.

⁶ The PFLP's founding statement as well as the documents of the second congress offer little perspective on a socioeconomic transformation of Palestinian society, except for when the second congress states that "the struggle for Palestine will, as regards the Palestinian and Arab masses, be a gateway towards the culture of the age and a transition from a state of under-development to the requirements of modern life."⁶ A year later, in its "Internal Structure" document of 1971, however, a democratic socialist Arab society is mentioned as the outcome of the liberation struggle.⁶ The PFLP pronounces therein a 2-phased strategy for liberation in Palestine and Arab peoples. For Arab peoples, the first phase is a national democratic revolution which will produce a dictatorship of the proletariat that will support the war of liberation against Zionism, while for Palestinians the first phase is one of national liberation. The second phase is building socialism in a united Arab world. In the politburo's 1977 report titled "The Revolution Continues for the Liberation of Man and Land," the PFLP announces economic struggle as a central action dialectically tied to the party's ideological and political struggle.⁶ In a 1979 document titled "A Discussion of the Palestinian Communist Organization Report in the West Bank" the PFLP implores the working class and its parties and allies to achieve the national and socialist revolutions as one operation in multiple phases, led by the working class.⁶

1. Models of building socialism in places like Korea, Vietnam, Yemen, and Cuba.⁷
2. Visions for the democratic national revolution in Arab countries, mainly Lebanon and Jordan.

Building Socialism

“We thank you for the lessons that we can glean from your experience. Witnessing your accomplishments impelled us to further struggle against murderous Zionism and imperialism that occupy our homeland, so that we can provide our people with liberty and then commence with a process of building similar to yours, and thus provide to our sons and mothers and children and people the happiness that the Korean revolution today provides to the sons and children of the Korean people.” —George Habash (PFLP’s secretary-general) during a visit to the Democratic People’s Republic of Korea (DPRK) in 1970.⁸

Apart from articles on revolutionary military strategy taken from revolutions around the world, *Al Hadaf* abounds with models of building socialism in its various phases. On this front, the DPRK, South Yemen (PDRY), and Vietnamese revolutions are the most studied, but others include Oman, China, Cambodia, Somalia, Cuba, and Philippines. These models are covered from slightly different angles, depending on each revolution. The Korean example is most often portrayed as a mature and triumphant socialist state that has achieved substantial industrialization, the Yemeni example is portrayed as another triumphant revolution in the early stages of building socialism, while Vietnam sits between the two. *Al Hadaf* repeatedly stresses the similarities of these revolutions’ contexts to the Arab world, thus arguing for the possibility of achieving similar outcomes through national democratic revolutions that emulate these models while caring for the Arab specificities.

Within these models of building socialism, the agrarian question assumes a lion’s share of focus, and so does industrial development; other topics of focus include planning, infrastructure and housing. Apart from these spatial dimensions, which are the focus of my research, ideological and cultural transformation are equally covered and women struggle is prevalent.

⁷ In Sayigh p. 350, the Chinese model is said to have been featured prominently in *al-Hadaf*’s early years. It might have been featured in the first 54 issues which I did not have access to at the time of writing this paper.

⁸ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 72, p. 10.

In a series of articles titled after Kim Il Sung's book *Theses on the Socialist Rural Question in Our Country* (where the line between Al-Hadaf's commentary and the borrowed content is not clear) the agrarian question is presented and explained as a central preoccupation of Marxism-Leninism and a prerequisite for a victorious socialist revolution—particularly in contexts of colonialism and postcolonialism—as well as for the phase of building socialism.⁹

The solution to the agrarian question is argued to be the obliteration of the difference between city and countryside, and between working class and peasants. This is then explained in detail from the context and history of Korea. Namely, the articles outline the steps as: developing agriculture and rural society in terms of ideology, culture, and technic (means of production and management), under the leadership of the urban working class and its party and state. Reorganizing peasant economy around collective production, via elective farmer cooperatives, is presented as the point of departure.

This presentation of the agrarian question and its solution follows directly Korean Three Revolutions model. And in fact, this model along with the Juche ideology are repeatedly praised in Al-Hadaf for their creative application of Marxism-Leninism.¹⁰

The agrarian question recurs in most articles on building socialism in Korea where it is treated in further detail. One article, for example, goes in detail on property ownership and the necessary existence of cooperative ownership in the countryside and nationalized ownership in the cities, with the differences that this entails.¹¹ It discusses the form of the cooperatives as well as the role of the state in managing the relationship between the countryside and the working class in a manner that ensures codependence under the leadership of the working class.

Similar topics are approached through the Yemeni revolution, which Al-Hadaf presents as an exemplar of the modern national democratic revolution (219).¹² In an article titled “The Agrarian Question in Democratic Yemen,” the Yemeni minister of information outlines the agrarian problem in Yemen, referring to its roots in colonial history.¹³ He presents a newly instated land reform law and explains the developments in this regard since the commencement of the revolution. In fact, several articles are dedicated to studying the Yemeni land laws in detail. In this

⁹ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 242-245, p. 13.

¹⁰ See for example: *Al-Hadaf*, no. 55, p. 16. It is worth noting the Hashim Ali Mohsen was the secretary-general of the ASAP.

¹¹ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 243, p. 13.

¹² *Al-Hadaf*, no. 219, p. 14.

¹³ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 88, p. 10.

article, as in others, farmer cooperatives are given great focus and their mechanisms of operation and benefits explained in detail as well as their history in Yemeni traditions.¹⁴ In another article, titled “Revolutionary Solutions to the Agrarian Question,” farmers’ role in the revolution is stressed, including their arrest of large property holders and their support to the government’s land redistribution efforts.¹⁵ Whereas in the Korean example the focus is on the state and its plans for the countryside, in the Yemeni case an equal focus is given to the role of the farmers themselves in enacting land reform. In the same vein, the topic of self-governance and grassroots organization in the countryside is highlighted, where in several articles the role of local committees and councils in political representation as well as development is explained.¹⁶ For example, one article describes how popular committees in the countryside became the authority on the ground, protecting cooperatives and the accomplishments of the “agrarian revolution,” and became the basis of local representation and political participation.¹⁷

Such issues of socioeconomic transformation—the agrarian question, property ownership, cooperative forms of production, and self-governance—are also highlighted in the Thufari/Omani and Somali revolutions, where the pastoral component of the countryside is discussed.¹⁸ Land reform is also mentioned from the context of the revolution in the Philippines, where it was enacted in the liberated “red bases”.¹⁹

Spatial planning is also broached in several articles on Yemen. Infrastructural development is presented as a tool for bridging the gap between the city and the countryside, encouraging cultural and material exchange, and thus contributing to solving the agrarian question.²⁰ The Yemeni experience of cooperation between the state and local rural volunteers in infrastructure construction is explained in other articles.²¹ Furthermore, architecture and real estate are treated in several articles such as one that analyzes architectural production in relation to the political economy of the colonial regime, and sets out future directions where quality housing should spread in the country, while discussing a new law banning real estate speculation in the country.²²

¹⁴ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 128, p. 4-5.

¹⁵ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 73, p. 5.

¹⁶ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 88, p. 10; no. 89, p. 10; no. 100, p. 9; no. 144, p.8.

¹⁷ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 88, p. 10.

¹⁸ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 257, p. 10; no. 228, p. 14.

¹⁹ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 192, p. 12.

²⁰ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 89, p. 10.

²¹ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 89, p. 10.

²² *Al-Hadaf*, no. 167, p. 8.

Similarly, in one article on Vietnam titled “How Shall We Build Socialism?” that treats the three aspects of the revolution (technical, ideological, cultural) spatial planning is foregrounded. The article states that:

“The best way to connect the city to the countryside and reduce the differences between them swiftly is by building a centrally run economy, and developing a regional economy as well...New cities will appear closer to the countryside. And based on economic development, we will build next to some relatively large cities which act as political cultural and economic hubs a great number of small and medium sized cities in different areas in order to influence and help develop rural areas in the economic social and cultural arenas at lightning speed. Then we change the face of the whole area and provide the people with materially decent life and a rich cultural life”.²³

In another article on Vietnam, housing is presented as a priority for the countryside as well as the cities and “a socialist art of building that conjoins national and modern traits” is declared as a goal.²⁴ Housing and spatial planning in general are treated with equal detail in other articles on Korea.²⁵

These are but a few examples, and *Al Hadaf* abounds with others. In numbers, within the 300 issues analyzed there were 58 articles specifically about building socialism. That is, one in every five issues of *Al Hadaf* spoke about models of building socialism. Amongst those articles, 23 were on Korea, 18 on Yemen, 8 on Vietnam, and 4 on Thufar/Oman. In each five articles on building socialism, three would discuss each of agriculture, land reform, or industry; two would mention the agrarian question specifically, and two would refer to the relationship between the city and the countryside, discuss cooperatives, or women struggle; while one would mention any of planning and architecture, infrastructure, housing, healthcare, feudalism, and self-governance.

While Sayigh shows in his book that the models of building socialism in the early years of the PFLP were a form of rhetorical competition over leftism with the splinter DFLP, his argument does not explain the persistence of such material in *Al-Hadaf* throughout the 1970s.²⁶ This leads us to ask for other explanations.

²³ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 75, p. 14.

²⁴ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 396, p. 27.

²⁵ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 244-246, p. 13-14.

²⁶ Sayigh, p. 350.

Those examples could have represented the PFLP's aspirations for second phase of the Palestinian revolution, given Habash's quote at the beginning and the PFLP's general strategy, yet one article on Vietnam hints to another possibility. In "Revolutionary Rule in Quang Tri Commune: Notes on the Margin of the Resistance's Relationship to the Masses in South Lebanon" Al-Hadaf presents the revolutionary transformations in the commune through the 10-point program announced by the interim revolutionary council of the district, which redistributed land and abolished laws that benefitted generals and feudalists, ensured democratic representation of the people, equality between men and women, freedom of religious expression, and abolished all forms of oppression instated by Saigon.²⁷ Al Hadaf states:

"This experience is highly valuable not only to the Vietnamese revolution, but for all revolutionary peoples, because fighters here are providing a model for the future they are fighting towards during the battle itself, and weaving with the masses a relationship that exemplifies the life that the revolutionaries build, in face of the kind of life the occupiers fight to preserve."²⁸

While care for the relationship with the masses fits into the Maoist strategy of the PFLP, this article hints to possible prefigurative voices in the party's publication. Did the PFLP actually follow this prefigurative approach? This remains to be seen.

Democratic National Revolution

But let us now turn to the second type of visions of social transformation that appear in Al-Hadaf, namely visions for democratic national revolution in Arab countries. Here, the PFLP's official positions are broad, but the opinion pieces Al-Hadaf published and the programs of its partners provide a rather clear vision of social transformation, particularly for Lebanon.

In one representative issue Habash, on a May Day speech in Ein el Hilweh, mentions the Arab working class and the intertwinement of the Palestinian and the Arab liberation struggles, but does not mention any goals for Arab struggle and keeps his focus on the role of the Palestinian working class in its liberation struggle.²⁹ Yet in the same issue we read a statement by the ASAP-L calling on the Lebanese working class to assume their historical role and continue the fight against "the regime of the 4%" to achieve the national democratic revolution and build

²⁷ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 159, p. 13.

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 251, p. 4.

socialism.³⁰ Another article analyzes the regressing path of the Arab petite bourgeoisie military regimes and states that the working class can and should assume responsibility to fight these regimes and implement its dictatorship, and develop their countries towards socialism.³¹

In another issue, an article by Haitham Kamal that analyzes the strategic situation of the Arab world and the Zionist threat, particularly for Lebanon, concludes with steps for the way forward. It proposes an alternative system for Lebanon which: “1. Ends foreign monopolies, 2. Economically annihilates the bourgeoisie, 3. Ends feudalism, 4. Enacts major changes in Lebanese agriculture, 5. Establishes military capabilities, and 6. Supports the Palestinian revolution.”³²

An article by an anonymous author, which analyzes the situation of a southern Lebanese village starts by announcing that the slogan for the period is “liberation from feudalism, social oppression, and colonialism,” and ends by indirectly setting the tasks as: “the need to swipe away the exploitative regime, and the local partners of imperialism—brokers and lords—and the need to build the democratic patriotic regime on its rubble, where feudalism is annihilated and the countryside is liberated completely from its relations and adopts instead democratic cooperative relations and collective farms and dense agriculture.”³³

In an article titled “The Vision of the ASAP: Lebanon of the Past and of the Future” the ASAP analyzes the class composition of Lebanese society, its antagonisms, and the prospects for social change.³⁴ The party announces its goal as to create a socialist classless society, and explains that before such a society is reached a mediating, interim society is needed, which shall be achieved through the national democratic revolution. Another article on the ASAP goes into further detail on their action and vision in Tyre during the first year of the civil war. There, the ASAP mentions its struggle against the Khalil’s (feudal lords) hegemony over the Tyre municipality, as well as its management of the port in the service of the classes the party represents. Furthermore, it discusses its policy on *musha’* land (commons), real estate, and housing.³⁵

³⁰ *Ibid*, p. 7.

³¹ *Ibid*, p. 12.

³² *Al-Hadaf*, no. 75, p. 7.

³³ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 115, p. 20.

³⁴ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 314, p. 12.

³⁵ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 346, p. 12.

In other articles, the political program of the Socialist Party of Lebanon and the National Federation of Trade Unions are presented and discussed, and there, issues of feudalism, development of the countryside, land use, factory worker rights, and other topics are treated.³⁶

Articles with visions of social transformation for the Arab countries are common in *Al-Hadaf*. Out of the 300 issues analyzed, there are at least 44 such articles, i.e. one article per seven issues. Twenty-eight of these articles were authored by the PFLP (or *Al-Hadaf*), while nine were by their partner, the Arab Socialist Action Party – Lebanon (ASAP-L).³⁷

Articles with visions of social transformation for the Arab countries are quite prevalent in *Al-Hadaf*. Out of the 300 issues analyzed, there are at least 44 such articles, i.e. one article per seven issues. Twenty-eight of these articles were authored by the PFLP (or *Al-Hadaf*), while nine were by their partner, the Arab Socialist Action Party – Lebanon (ASAP-L).³⁸

These visions for Lebanon approach a number of the topics previously discussed from the context of other model revolutions, such as the agrarian question. For example, class struggle appears ten times; economic development, agriculture, farmers, feudalism, and land reform four times each; healthcare, factory workers, self-governance, and cooperatives three times each; while housing and infrastructure development at least once each.

But the treatment of social issues in *Al-Hadaf* is not limited to visions of the national democratic revolution, as articles, reports, and studies of the social conditions of the masses in Lebanon, and to a lesser degree Jordan and the OPT, were prevalent in the magazines. As we can see in the diagram³⁹

Conclusion

The PFLP presented visions of socioeconomic transformation in *Al-Hadaf* via: models for building socialism, and visions for Arab revolutions. The two indirect forms of

³⁶ *Al-Hadaf*, no. 217, p. 7; no. 364, p. 6; no. 115, p. 7.

³⁷ The Arab Socialist Action Party (ASAP) was founded by George Habash as the Leftist reincarnation of the Movement of Arab Nationalists; the ASAP-L was the Lebanese branch of the ASAP, much like the PFLP was considered to be its Palestinian branch.

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³⁹ In numbers, for every ten issues of *Al-Hadaf*, three articles would revolve around class struggle and one would talk about factory workers. And for every twenty issues, there would be one article that treats each of feudalism, farmers, agriculture, healthcare, or industry.

socioeconomically transformative visions that the PFLP presented in *al Hadaf* point to some main points:

The persistence of such material in *Al-Hadaf* throughout the 1970s deserves attention and points to reasons other than rhetorical competition with the DFLP, possibly they were intended as visions or myths of liberation, possibly there were other reasons, this remains in need of further investigation.⁴⁰

The role that models of building socialism played in influencing the actions of the PFLP or its base particularly in the OPT, and the extent to which visions for Lebanon were put to action also remain topics for further research beyond the corpus of the magazine. A few initial observations point to the potential of such an endeavor:

In an investigation I am currently undertaking of the cooperatives set up in the 1980s by the PFLP in the OPT, participants interviewed often returned to the agrarian question along with the revolutionary tools to address it—often circling back to models presented in *Al-Hadaf*. For example, W.R referred to the Yugoslav cooperative model and stated that the organization educated and mobilized its cadre towards cooperatives.⁴¹ A.S, advocated for a developmental model that evoked several aspects of the models covered in *Al-Hadaf* (particularly those of Yemen on the topic cooperatives, but also Korea).⁴²

With regards to the PFLP's action in Lebanon, my research has led me to a case where the PFLP and along with the ASAP-L have dispossessed Al Khalil feudal lords of lands near Tyre and redistributed the land amongst peasants.⁴³ This points to one attempt at radical socio-economic transformation, and points to the need to look beyond the camps and Palestinians in analyzing the presence and role of the PFLP in Lebanon.

Needless to say, these are anecdotes and pointers in need of much further investigation, particularly given the divergence between the PFLP's organizations in the OPT and the diaspora.

⁴⁰ Sayigh, p. 350.

⁴¹ Interview with author, 31.7.2020.

⁴² Interview with author, 7.8.2020.

⁴³ As'ad Abu Khalil, email correspondence 21.10.2019.